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Lightweight cementless aerated concrete – An overview

^{*1}**N. Anuja**

Assistant Professor (Senior Grade), Department of Civil Engineering
Mepco Schlenk Engineering College, Sivakasi, Virudhunagar District, Tamil Nadu, India

²**J. Christebel Rose**

PG Student, Department of Civil Engineering Mepco Schlenk Engineering College, Sivakasi, Virudhunagar
District, Tamil Nadu, India

**Corresponding Author: N. Anuja
Email: anu_priya1031@yahoo.com*

Abstract:

In recent years, the development of sustainable materials as an alternative to cement concrete has received more attention. Geopolymer concrete is an emerging material which is found to be a better alternative for ordinary concrete. Addition of foaming agents in geopolymer can further decrease the thermal conductivity without compromising its mechanical properties. There will be a reduction in density, compressive strength, thermal conductivity and also an increase in porosity with foam addition. In this paper, a collective work on different foaming agents that are preferably used along with geopolymer mix was discussed in detail. Based on the foaming method, the mechanical and microstructure properties get varies. The foam-based concrete will show better performance in thermal resistance and low density when compared to lightweight aggregate concrete. Due to its low density, it will reduce the dead weight and improve the thermal insulation property of the building.

Keywords:

Geopolymer concrete, Foam, lightweight, compressive strength, thermal resistance.

1. Introduction:

The emission of greenhouse gases has become one of the major sources of ozone depletion. The growth of a nation is defined by the infrastructure development of the county. The construction sector has a significant role in the development of Infrastructure. Cement has become the main source of construction, but cement production plays a major role in the carbon footprint along with the exhausting abundance of raw materials. The cement manufacturing process starts from the mining of raw materials to the process of calcination in clinker(1), throughout this process the liberation of CO₂ is about 0.5-0.6 tons per ton of cement. Due to swift urbanization and economic boom, the need for cementitious products has increased (1). The increase in the requirement for concrete usage in various applications has resulted in an increment in the production of cement (2). The research in alternative cementitious has led to the utilization of industrial by-products (3). Green materials have been used as an alternate source for cement and to promote sustainable development (4). One of the developing green materials is geopolymer concrete or zero cement concrete.

Joseph Davidovits a French scientist, developed Geopolymer in 1978 as a binder (5). Geopolymer is an inorganic polymeric gel. Polycondensation reaction of alumino- silicate and alkali activator forms geopolymer. Due to the polycondensation, an amorphous /semi-crystalline three-dimensional inorganic structure (5), (6) is formed by the combination of (SiO₄)⁴⁻ and (AlO₄)⁴⁻ is linked by sharing oxygen(3), (4). By the presence of positive ions (Na⁺, K⁺, Li⁺, Ca²⁺, Ba²⁺) cavities of the framework will be equal to the negative charge Al³⁺ in IV-fold coordination (5), (7). Raw materials used for the copolymerization process should be rich in aluminosilicate content (Fly ash, metakaolin, Silica fume, GGBS) and dissolved in an alkali solution (NaOH, KOH) leading to the formation of monomers of aluminate and silicate(2). There will be a change in properties based on the difference in the source material. The exact geopolymerization reaction is still not defined. Depending on Si/Al ratio that is amorphous to semi-crystalline the geopolymer structure is divided into three (5).

Poly (silicate) (-Si-O-Al-O)

Poly (silicate -siloxo) (-Si-O-Al-O-Si-O-)

Poly (sialate-disiloxo) (-Si-O-Al-O-Si-O-Si-O)

M_p ((SiO₂)_z AlO₂)_p. WH₂O is the empirical formula for polysilicate, where P is the degree of polycondensation, z = 1,2,3 (Si/Al ratio)(4), (5). Nucleation and growth of the aluminosilicate chain get affected by the differences in alkali cations due to size, density, and so on (8). Na +

cation is more active and effective in the dilution process than K^+ because Na^+ (116 pm) ions are smaller than K^+ (152 pm)cations. The main binding compound (N-A-S-H) hydrous alkali aluminosilicate is the feature of gel formation. In recent time's researchers and the construction sector got attracted to geopolymers because of their distinguished performance of mechanical and durability properties.

Energy consumption and sustainability grabbed the attention of researchers to construct an energy-efficient building. Lightweight construction has become a remarkable development it is more popular in the construction of tall buildings, precast wall elements, bridge embankments, sub- bases in highways. Lightweight will reduce the dead load of the building, improves thermal insulation, and excellent acoustic shielding (9). Improving the thermal resistivity of exterior walls is an effective approach to reducing the energy consumption of a building (10). Lightweight concrete is categorized into three No fines concrete - coarse aggregate which passes through 20mm sieve and retains on 10mm sieve is used in this concrete mix, Lightweight Aggregate - is the replacement of normal aggregate (expanded clay, expanded glass, slate, perlite), Foamed concrete – the artificial foaming agent is to entrap the air and which creates pores after hydration(11). According to ACI 213R, the 28 days compressive strength of a cylinder should be 17 MPa with a density of 1120 to 1920 kg/m^3 . In the case of, without strength requirement, the density can be 800 to 2240 kg /m^3 (12). Because of its great thermal insulation properties and the light in weight incorporation of lightweight materials with geopolymer will improve the thermal and acoustic properties and will make a lightweight geopolymer concrete (13).

2. Types of Foaming:

2.1. Chemical Foaming:

The most common type of foam agents is hydrogen peroxide, sodium perborate, and aluminium powder. Along with foaming agents, lightweight aggregates are also combined to make lightweight concrete. In hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) the oxygen will be realized along with water in the decomposition process and the oxygen will create air voids (14).

The size of pores will be smaller in H_2O_2 than pores created in aluminum. (15) The distribution of pores will be more uniform the decomposition rate depends on the concentration of H_2O_2 ,

alkali solution, and rate of geopolymerization reaction(16). In aluminium, due to releasing of hydrogen gas, voids are generated (14)

When aluminium is added to geopolymer, the alkali solution will act as a catalyst and helps in the formation of hydrogen gas, and produce a precipitate of aluminium hydroxide with the recreation alkali (17). Strength development in geopolymer matrix will get delayed by the addition of aluminium powder (17). The mechanical and thermal properties depend on the density of the foaming agent. The air bubbles will be almost in spherical shape and have a size between 0.1 and 1mm. When more amount of foaming agent is added the volume of pores will be increased but there will be a decrease in the count of pores due to cluster of foams (15).

2.2. Mechanical Foaming:

Mechanical foaming is categorized as mixed foaming and pre-foaming. Surfactant (Sodium dodecyl sulfate, sodium alkylbenzene sulfonate) is added during the mixing process, and foam will be generated in mixed foaming (18). In pre-foaming pre-made foam will be added to the cement slurry(11). The mixing speed is important for the production of bubble creation(18). Surfactants are classified as anionic, cationic, and non-ionic. Based on the type of surfactant, the volume of pores, distribution, and size differ. Surfactant molecule has a hydrophilic head group and hydrophobic tail (19). The cell size will be controlled and the surface tension will get reduced depending on the amount of surfactant (19). There will be an effect on thermal properties due to the rise in atmospheric humidity. By using a non-ionic surfactant the porosity can be increased (18).

2.3. Syntactic Foaming:

Other than that chemical and mechanical foaming syntactic foaming can also be synthesized by adding hollow spheres to the binding agent. Cenosphere, hollow polymeric microsphere, and ceramic are common particles used for syntactic foam (20). Cenosphere is a hollow microsphere where inert gas will be filled it has less weight and is spherical in shape (21). By increasing the content there will be a decrease in the density of the geopolymer foam. Ceramic foam is fabricated by impregnated by using the replica technique. Open-cell geopolymers are formed which have greater porosity than 70% in volume (22). Table.1 depicts the overview of commercial geopolymer foam concrete.

Table. 1: Overview of commercial geopolymer foam concrete

Alumino silicate Source	Alkaline Activator	Foaming Agent	Curing Conditions			Physical Properties			Mechanical Strength		Ref
			Curing Method	Temp (°C)	Time (hr)	Dry Density (kg/m ³)	Porosity (% mm)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mk)	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	
Metakaolin	Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Silicate	Hydrogen Peroxide	Standard Curing Room	20		234.7	12.5-17.5	0.058	2.6	3.1	[10]
Fly Ash F	Sodium Hydroxide	Aluminium powder, Hydrogen peroxide	Oven curing	70	24	610 to 1000	44.9		2.9 to 9.3		[15]
Fly Ash F	Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Silicate, Calcium hydroxide	Surfactant- Sodium dodecyl sulphate	Thermal Chamber	25		430-460	17		18.5		[9]
Fly Ash F	Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Silicate	Conplast F292(M)	Oven curing	65-70	24	1193 - 1344	13		6.1	1.08	[23]
Ground Granulated Blast Furnace, Fly Ash F	Sodium metasilicate anhydrous powder	Sodium dodecyl sulphate	Ambient curing			562.4	67.2	0.25	1.38		[24]
Fly Ash F, Palm oil fuel ash	Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Silicate	Sika AER 50/50	Curing Chamber	65	48	1314	25	0.47	8.32	1.48	[25]
Metakaolin	Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Silicate	Hydrogen peroxide	Oven curing	70	48	295		0.107	1.92		[26]
Fly Ash F	Potassium Hydroxide, Potassium Silicate	Silica fume		40	24	1170	18.1		8.9		[13]
Fly Ash C	Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Silicate	Calcium Sulfoaluminate	Oven Curing	60	24	1667	6.78		18.2		[11]
Fly Ash	Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Silicate	Silicon	Ambient	22	24	525		0.254	5.3		[27]
Metakaolin, Fly Ash F	Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Silicate	Hydrogen peroxide	Ambient curing		2	615	3.86	0.195	5.4	2.4	[16]
Fly Ash F, GGBS	Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Silicate	Hydrogen peroxide, Cenosphere	Ambient curing	20	24	405.73	33.88	0.11	3.4	1.2	[20]
Metakaolin, Bagasse Ash	Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Silicate	Hydrogen peroxide	Oven Curing	50	24	640-1270	31.46-68.67	0.3	13.2		[28]
Fly Ash, GBFS	Sodium Metasilicate Powder	Cenosphere	Ambient curing			978		0.28	17.5		[21]

Fly Ash, Hollow microsphere	Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Silicate	Hydrogen peroxide	Oven curing	60	24	200		0.05223	1.06	0.51	[29]
Fly Ash	Sodium Silicate	sodium dodecyl sulfate	Oven curing	70	24		76	0.127	0.719		[30]

3. Foam stability:

The nucleating agent can be used to accelerate the setting time and the bubble collapse can be reduced (31). The pores in hardened concrete can be increased by the addition of stabilizing agent (32). Mechanical foaming has finer and more stable bubbles compared to chemical foaming due to its reliable control of properties (9). The collapse in foam occurs due to coalescence, drainage, and Ostwald ripening (9). The formation of smaller bubbles will be hard and rapidly vanish and there will be excess drainage and frequent film rupture with large bubbles. Stabilization of the foam will provide a homogeneous pore distribution and tailor the pours structure (33). Vegetable oil, proteins, surfactants, etc have been used as stabilizing agents (26). Surface tension between gas-liquid interfaces gets reduced and it helps in stabilizing the bubble this can be achieved by surfactant.

Foams with big pores easily get broken under pressure. If a system is prepared with no stability agent the gas-liquid interface will provide a thicker wall between the cellular structures to prevent the leakage of fluid, which leads to coalescing of bubbles (33). Due to the stability agent, the modification of viscosity based on slurry condition will change bubble size (33). It will be less homogenous and due to the coalescence of bubbles, it will generate interconnected cellular structure (18). The stability agent can be added less than 1.5wt % higher than will cause the formation of a thin layer and lower strength. The stability of chemical foam depends on the fresh performance of the concrete (20). Fluidity will be the key factor for stability if fluidity is high the bubble gather together and cause coalescence (20). Silica fume is thermally stable up to 800°C beyond that it gets soften like glass (34).

4. Discussion in the physical and mechanical properties of geopolymer foam concrete:

4.1. Dry density, water absorption:

In general, porous concrete absorb more water than ordinary concrete and the density of porous concrete will be low. There will not be any influence of alkaline activator in density. The durability of the concrete is related to water absorption and density. There will be an effective

decrease in density due to the decomposition of H_2O_2 because of close pore formation. For the mass ratio of 1.0 % expanded polystyrene, the density is reduced to 83.3% (10). There is an increase in water absorption as expanded polystyrene gets increased but there is improvement in the impermeability of concrete because polystyrene is hydrophobicity in nature (16). There will be an increase in density in the bottom layer due to solids from the interstitial paste drainage (35). The specific gravity of the binder will affect the density of the concrete (36). The water absorption of 20% replacement of palm oil fuel ash is about 42%. Compared with obtained results ambient curing results in an increase in air capillaries leading to a raise in water absorption (23).

Based on the oven-dry density the water absorption get varies. Expanded Perlite reduces the density of the geopolymer matrix which results in the uplift of air bubbles to the top and movement of binder towards down (37). When there increase in foaming agents from 0.003-0.012 there will be a reduction in density up to 65%. An increase in H_2O_2 leads to an increase in pores content and the water absorption is raised by 64% (26). Hybrid foam with a density of 0.3 -0.7 shows homogeneous and regular voids with uniform distribution (27). By utilization of more water content low density can be achieved in the case of aerated geopolymer(38). The density gets reduced by 8.53% for full replacement of the cenosphere and there will be slight raise in water absorption this is due to the interconnection of bubbles(21). Water absorption can be reduced by the addition of fibers. The density will depend on mass loss and volume expansion due to the curing process (34). Usually, foam on top is lighter and foam on the bottom will be closed cells because the pores are trapped and it will be difficult to mature and get coarser (39).

4.2. Mechanical properties:

A decrease in strength can be absorbed with an increase in the percentage of river sediments from 30 to 70 %, and there will be a fall in flexural strength due to the low activity of river sediment (10). The density will be increased in the case of the addition of aluminium powder (17). Strength development will be low in the early stage of the reaction and gel formation will be developed in a later stage the delay in strength development is due to the slow dissolution of fly ash particles with Al and it slows down the polymeric reaction (17). Mechanical properties will depend on density, strength will get raised as density will be raised. An increase in strength can be observed in the increase in the quantity of bagasse ash but will long-term curing there won't be any significant raise in strength in case of short-term curing. There will be a decrease in porosity when increase in bagasse ash. The addition of 30% bagasse ash and 1 % H_2O_2 was the optimum mix with acceptable density and compressive strength (28). In the

case of fresh geopolymer mortar increase of H_2O_2 cause a raise in the air bubble and affects the compressive strength (28), (40).

Strength depends on the number of bubbles in a matrix beside that the alkaline activator ratio also contributes to the strength development by increasing the geopolymerization(33). Due to high carbon content, the rate of reaction and microstructure will get affected(23). Heat curing process helps in achieving early strength by polymerization process thus oil palm shell foamed geopolymer concrete achieves early strength (25). There will be a reduction in strength due to the coalescence of bubbles and it produces larger voids and wide distribution of void size (15). Flexural strength also gets reduced with the increase in air voids it will be interrelated to porosity (14). Silica fume will not reduce the open porosity and this property will enhance the compressive strength at 28 days of curing (13). If there is a decrease in surface tension there will be a decrease in the cell size of the foam and load distribution will be uniform in the case of small cells which will be even in size (41). There will be a decrease in strength due to the unburnt carbon that absorbs the activator solution. The required amount of water content will be increased with higher carbon content. 50% replacement by cenosphere has increased the strength to 54.63% (20). Addition of basalt, PVA fiber of 0.5-2 wt % increases the compressive strength and an increase in the range of fiber increases the strength (30).

4.3. Thermal Conductivity:

Thermal conductivity is directly related to dry density that reduction in density will reduce the thermal conductivity. By the addition of river sediment from 30-70% there will be a reduction in thermal conductivity at the same time addition of expanded polystyrene with foam concrete reduce the density significantly the thermal conductivity also gets reduced by comparing both river sediment gives better thermal conductivity and suitable for higher temperature and humidity environment(10). The thermal conductivity depends on the morphology of the structure. The increased porosity will decrease the thermal conductivity the gas phase takes up relatively smaller space than the solid phase (29). When 1 -1.5wt% of H_2O_2 is added the rate of thermal conductivity has reduced. Foamed concrete exhibits good thermal conductivity due to the cellular microstructure (28). The oil palm shell foamed geopolymer concrete shows 48% low thermal conductivity than conventional blocks (25).

Addition of rice husk from 0.08-0.24 the thermal conductivity varied from 0.095 to 0.118 W/mk increase in rice husk increased the conductivity as rice husk has poor thermal insulation but in the case of the addition of foaming agent from 0.003- 0.012 there is a decrease in thermal conductivity of 45% (26). In hybrid geopolymer foam when the foaming agent is reduced and

the lightweight aggregate is added the density is increased with raise in conductivity (27). Cenosphere is a hollow structure therefore the thermal conductivity is also decreased due to a decrease in density (20). 15-30% synthesis of phase-changing material with foam geopolymer has reduced them to 1.85 -3.76 °C and there is an enhancement in thermal storage capacity by 105–181 % (42). The particle size of aerogel decides the thermal conductivity, an increase in particle size decrease the conductivity finer particles have more interfacial area with geopolymer which increases conductivity (43). There will decrease in conductivity due to an increase in fiber size this is due to the packing of fiber in the geopolymer matrix (12).

5. Conclusion:

- The compressive strength and density will be directly proportional. An increase in density increases compressive strength and stiffness increment can also be obtained. There will be enhanced strength due to finer and homogenous pores.
- Foam stability has to be considered to get uniform pores size and smooth geometry. Based on the ratio of the foaming agent and method of foaming the stability will change.
- Reduction in heat of hydration can be done by reducing the volume of the foaming agent.
- Thermal conductivity is directly proportional to the bulk density which increases in density decreases the porosity and increases thermal conductivity. There is a deduction in conductivity in foam concrete due to low heat transfer between the solid phases.
- The addition of lightweight aggregates has increased the density and thermal conductivity than the addition of foam. The strength depends on the density and based on the dosage of foam the densities get varies.
- The interconnected capillarity pores and non-capillarity pores have a major part in water absorption. The foam has a lower density so it tends to float but due to the heavy density of the binder it moves downward thus density will be lower at the top and higher in the bottom layer.

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